

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

A NEURO-FUZZY MODEL FOR PREDICTING SUCCESSFUL PASSING OF ENTRANCE EXAMS OF APPLICANTS TO HIGHER EDUCATION.

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Abstract. This scientific article describes the development of a neuro-fuzzy system for predicting the success of applicants in university entrance exams. In the study, the ANFIS model was used to predict the applicant's probability of success in the upcoming exam based on the average grade at school, the period of preparation for the exam, the applicant's experience, and other factors. Data from 256 applicants who applied for the 2022 entrance exam in Uzbekistan were collected as a database. 80% of this data was used for model training and 20% for model testing.

The study highlights the possibilities of using neuro-fuzzy systems in the field of education to create opportunities for applicants to choose the right higher education institution for the upcoming exam. The ANFIS model's inclusion of quantitative and qualitative data, as well as its adaptability to changing conditions, make it a promising tool for predicting applicant success in different contexts. An experiment was conducted comparing the performance of the ANFIS model with prediction models such as LinearRegression, Random Forest, XGBoost, DecisionTreeRegressor, and K-nearest Neighbors. The results showed that the ANFIS model outperformed the other models and showed high accuracy in predicting the scores that the applicants could score.

Overall, the paper provides valuable insights into the potential of neuro-fuzzy systems to predict academic success.

Keywords. ANFIS, prediction, GPA, Neuro-fuzzy system, Mamdani and Sugeno methods, Abiturent, Higher education.

Introduction. Entrance exams to higher education institutions in Uzbekistan are held once a year. Failure of applicants to successfully pass the exams of their chosen institutions may cause applicants to lose a year's worth of time. Therefore, it is important for applicants to choose the institution that suits them based on their capabilities and for higher education institutions. However, the literature on the use of neuro-fuzzy systems to predict the success of applicants in higher education entrance exams is still relatively limited. To help applicants make informed decisions, researchers have explored the use of advanced technologies such as neuro-fuzzy systems to predict the likelihood of success on entrance exams. Current research shows that predictive modeling using neuro-fuzzy systems is considered effective in improving applicants' success. Furthermore, the findings in this study provide valuable insights into the potential of neuro-fuzzy systems to predict academic success in a variety of contexts. In addition to education, the presented model can be used in various fields, such as finance and healthcare, where predictive modeling is becoming more and more important.

Literature analysis. In their research, Riyadh Mehdi and Mirna Nachouki used the

Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS) methodology to analyze and predict the Grade Point Average (GPA) of students enrolled in the Information Technology Program at Ajman University. He noted the advantage of the ANFIS model compared to other predictive models of artificial intelligence[1]. In addition, Al-Hammadi, A.S., and Milne, R.H. presented the design and development of a neuro-fuzzy classification method for predicting student performance in an engineering college. Neuro-fuzzy classification classifiers have been developed to help describe student performance. This method allows students to analyze their performance based on expected results and identify students who are suitable for future changes. This method can be used to assess student performance, determine admission procedures, and assess eligibility for entrance examinations.[2]. Amal AlGhamdi and others propose a machine learning approach to predict student admissions to graduate school, helping graduates identify and target universities that best fit their profiles. The study evaluates three regression strategies for predicting graduate school enrollment and concludes that the logistic regression model is the most effective in

predicting students' graduate school enrollment.[3]. In their research, I. Hatzilygeroudis et al presented an expert system called PASS to predict the probability of passing the Greek higher education national exams. The system makes predictions based on various types of student data [4]. Steven Walczak and Terry Sincic review the use of neural networks to predict students' probability of entering university and compare the method to traditional logistic regression modeling[5]. Although there are few instructions in the literature for the use of neuro-fuzzy systems in predicting students' admission to the university, this system is widely used in other fields. For example, in a study by Pamucar, D., Bozanic, D., et al., a neuro-fuzzy system was presented to predict the success of a construction company in public tenders. The system is designed to evaluate the company's position in the market and enables its stable operation. The model was developed using seven years of survey data, with the first six years used for model calibration and the last year for testing and validation. The system is optimized using the Artificial Bee Colony algorithm[6]. The research was conducted by Polshchikov K., Zdorenko Y., and others on the development of a neuro-fuzzy prediction system for accurate prediction of network load on a telecommunications channel. The use of the system is achieved by predicting the number of packets to be received in a given time interval to ensure the efficient transmission of data packets.[7]. In general, the methodologies of the neuro-fuzzy system develop according to the field of knowledge, and with the help of the neuro-fuzzy system, various social science methodologies can be implemented. The ability to constantly learn and adapt is seen as the driving force behind the development of neuro-fuzzy systems methodologies and their use in future intelligent applications. Provides a valuable resource for researchers and practitioners in the field of neuro-fuzzy systems.[8].

Research methodology. ANFIS is a powerful hybrid methodology that leverages the strengths of neural networks and fuzzy logic systems to improve the accuracy and efficiency of prediction mechanisms. Its versatility and flexibility make it a valuable tool in data analysis and predictive modeling. Neural networks, on the other hand, can effectively model complex relationships between input data and output

predictions. Fuzzy inference systems combined with neural networks increase the accuracy and robustness of predictive models[9]. ANFIS iteratively changes its parameters using examples provided to the system in order to minimize the error. It can effectively learn the characteristics of a particular algorithm and improve the accuracy of its predictions. Thus, based on the available data of the applicants, a model for predicting the score that they can collect at the time of admission was developed. By predicting their scores, one can infer their success in entrance exams.

Mamdani and Sugeno methods are two popular approaches used in fuzzy logic systems.

Mamdani's method is a type of fuzzy inference system that includes a rule-based approach, where the rules are expressed in natural language. It includes four main steps: Fuzzy clustering, rule evaluation, clustering, and defuzzification. The input variables are transformed into fuzzy sets by assigning linguistic symbols described by fuzzy membership functions, and then the rules are evaluated using fuzzy logic operations. The rule evaluation results are then summarized and defuzzified to obtain precise results[10], [11].

On the other hand, the Sugeno method is a type of fuzzy inference system based on a more mathematical approach. It includes two main stages: classification into fuzzy sets and rule evaluation. However, instead of aggregating and Fuzzification rule scores as in the Mamdani method, Sugeno's method uses a weighted average of the rule results to arrive at the final result. This method is also known as the Takagi-Sugeno-Kanga (TSK) fuzzy model.[12].

The main functional difference between Mamdani and Sugeno fuzzy systems lies in the output membership functions. While Mamdani output membership functions can take any functional form, Sugeno output membership functions are restricted to linear or continuous functional forms.

The Sugeno Fuzzy Inference System (FIS) performs better than the Mamdani FIS in terms of computational efficiency, prediction accuracy, and robustness when processing different input data[1], [13]. In this study, the ANFIS methodology based on the Sugeno FIS model was used to predict the score that applicants can get in the entrance exams to higher education institutions. As a result, predicting the output value

based on several different influencing factors for predicting the total score is proven to be more effective than other prediction models such as

LinearRegression, Random Forest, XGBoost, DecisionTreeRegressor, and K-nearest Neighbors.

Figure 1. Architecture of a Sugeno neuro-fuzzy inference system.

The structure of ANFIS membership to the first-order Sugeno fuzzy model with three membership functions for each input is shown in Figure 1. In the network, the input layer is given in blue and can be n . In our example, the input values are 5. And in green is the layer of membership functions membership to the input values. In this case, the number of membership functions may be different depending on the characteristics of the input values. The rules layer is shown in yellow. The total number of rules is

$$i = \prod_{j=1}^n x_j^{\mu} \quad (1)$$

where is x_j^{μ} the number of membership functions per input. n is the number of input values. The defuzzification layer is given in gray color and has a value equal to the number of rules.

The rule base for the first-order Sugeno fuzzy model is expressed as follows:

Q_1 : if x_1M_1 and x_2M_1 and $x_3M_1 \dots x_nM_1$ then $f_1 = p_{11} * x_1 + p_{12} * x_2 + \dots + p_{1n} * x_n + q_1$

Q_2 : if x_1M_1 and x_2M_1 and $x_3M_1 \dots x_nM_2$ then $f_2 = p_{21} * x_1 + p_{22} * x_2 + \dots + p_{2n} * x_n + q_2$ (2)

Q_i : if x_1M_j and x_2M_j and $x_3M_j \dots x_nM_j$ then $f_i = p_{i1} * x_1 + p_{i2} * x_2 + \dots + p_{in} * x_n + q_i$

The choice of fitness functions can affect the performance of ANFIS. Gaussian membership functions, when used with the Sugeno learning engine, perform better than other membership functions such as trim. Using Gaussian functions allows the learning algorithm to use all the data in

the training set to calculate the result of each rule, which leads to increased efficiency.

Based on the study by Sambariya and Prasad, it can be concluded that the ANFIS model can perform well when the input range is defined by three to five membership functions using Gaussian membership functions[14]. This shows that the choice of membership functions and their number can significantly affect the performance of ANFIS models.

In the research work, the database consists of ambiguous information. Here, membership functions serve to convert fuzzy values into numerical data for analysis.

$$\mu_{nj} = \exp \left[- \left(\frac{x - m}{\sqrt{2}\delta} \right)^2 \right] \quad j \in [1:5] \quad (3)$$

Here, m and δ are the values of the average variance of the Gaussian function, respectively. n and j denote the number of membership functions.

The samples converted from the fuzzy terms to the values of the membership function μ_{nj} generate a signal membership to the degree of fulfillment of the fuzzy rule in the next layer. It represents the defined value of the fuzzy rule relative to the predicted value.

$$w_i = \prod_n \mu_{M_j}(x_n) \quad j \in [1:5] \quad (4)$$

The w_i value needs to be normalized so that the output value of the ANFIS model falls within a certain range and can be interpreted correctly.

$$\bar{w}_i = \frac{w_i}{\sum w_i} \quad (5)$$

Here it calculates the ratio of i-rule strength to the total sum of strengths of all rules.

The ANFIS algorithm adjusts these parameters based on the input-output data pairs in the training set to minimize the total error between the predicted and actual output values. This value $\bar{w}_i * f_i = \bar{w}_i (p_{i1} * x_1 + p_{i2} * x_2 + .. + p_{in} * x_n + q_i)$ (6)

Here, the values given to the parameters p_{in} and q_i are determined during the training of the ANFIS model. The ANFIS model uses a hybrid learning algorithm that combines the backpropagation algorithm and the least squares method to optimize the values of these parameters[15]. The training process involves presenting the ANFIS model with input-output pairs and adjusting the values of the parameters to minimize the difference between the predicted output and the actual value. The q_i parameter is usually determined by the minimum value of the output membership function. For example, if the output membership function is a Gaussian function, the value of q_i is equal to the mean of the Gaussian function. p_{in} values are determined using the least squares method during training.

The last layer of the ANFIS model contains a single node, denoted Σ , that sums all the input signals to calculate the final output. This node is

responsible for combining the individual results of all the rules and producing the final result. The value calculated by the Σ node is the predicted value of the ANFIS model.[16].

$$\sum_i \bar{w}_i * f_i = \frac{\sum_i w_i * f_i}{\sum_i w_i} \quad (7)$$

In this study, an ANFIS was developed to predict the score that applicants are likely to score in the entrance exams.

Data analysis. To achieve this goal, the design of the models was carried out in several stages. First of all, the factors that have the strongest influence on the final result were studied. In his scientific research, Hirokawa considered the issue of determining the most important characteristics in predicting the academic performance of students.[17]. The results showed that behavioral attributes had the highest importance, followed by demographic attributes. The study highlights the importance of considering various factors in predicting academic performance and the potential utility of machine learning techniques for this purpose. Based on this, demographic and behavioral attributes were selected for applicants to score effectively in the exam. In addition, the influence factors of each attribute on the result were determined using the correlation coefficient. Table 1 below shows the coefficient of influence of each input parameter on the result.

Table 1

N _o	Input values	Correlation coefficient
	Average grade at school	0,67
	Exam preparation period	0,71
	Applicants experience	0,51
	Ability to remember	0,57
	The applicants level of information acceptance	0,62

It can be seen from the table that all 5 selected values are positively related to the result. The strongest correlation was found between the exam preparation period and the applicant's average school performance, with a correlation coefficient of 0,71, indicating a strong positive correlation. This shows that the more time an applicant prepares for the exam, the higher the probability of success.

School grade point average also shows a strong positive correlation with a coefficient of 0,67. The points acquired by applicants in school

courses are closely related to the points they can get in the exam.

The applicants level of information acceptance has an average positive correlation - 0.62, which indicates that quick learning of questions during exam preparation is important for the result.

Applicants' recall ability and experience have a moderate effect on the result, correlation coefficients are 0.57 and 0.51, respectively. This suggests that recall and experience may play a lesser role in applicant success than other factors.

Overall, these correlation coefficients indicate that the factors included in the model are positively related to applicant success.

Defining the membership functions for the input values is a crucial step in the development of the ANFIS model. Membership functions are used to determine the degree to which an input value affects the output. In other words, the membership functions determine the membership values of each input variable to a certain fuzzy set. This membership value is then used to determine the extent to which the input variable affects the output.

Choosing input values with high correlation coefficients is important because it ensures that the model is trained on the most relevant and influential features. In this study, the five input values with the highest correlation coefficients were selected, which are the average grade in school, the period of preparation for the exam, the experience of the student, the ability to remember and the level of information acceptance of the applicant.

After the input values were selected, their membership functions were determined by trial and error. This involved testing different membership functions and adjusting their parameters until the model produced accurate results.

In general, choosing the most appropriate input values and defining their membership functions is a crucial step in developing an accurate ANFIS model.

Predictive modeling and data analysis are used for different modeling purposes. While predictive modeling aims to predict output values based on input values, data analysis is about understanding the relationships between different variables and how they affect each other. These models can be used to test hypotheses, identify important factors affecting the system, and gain a deeper understanding of the underlying processes that drive system behavior. Both types of modeling can be useful in different contexts and can provide useful insights into the data being analyzed [18], [19]. The difference between data analysis and predictive modeling lies in their goals. Predictive modeling aims to predict new or future observations based on input variables, while data analysis aims to identify underlying causal relationships between input and output variables. Predictive modeling primarily uses associations

between variables, while data analysis emphasizes causation. Performance metrics also differ between the two types of modeling, with predictive models relying on data from test or validation sets, while data analysis uses different statistical methods to determine cause-and-effect relationships. [18]–[20].

The bottom line is that in predictive modeling, it is important to use test data to evaluate the predictive ability of the model, as the performance calculated from the training data will be overly optimistic. On the other hand, in data analysis, metrics are calculated by re-running the model on the training data to assess the explanatory power of the individual input variables. It is essential to use appropriate metrics in both modeling approaches to ensure proper estimation of model performance and contribution of input variables. [18]–[21].

Figure 2. Actual and predicted value.

Results and discussion. The research is aimed at predicting the score that applicants can get in the entrance exams to higher education institutions and evaluating the effectiveness of the proposed model for data analysis. The results of applying the model to other data sets were also checked to ensure consistency. For model estimation, methods such as MAE, MSE and RMSE were compared. In general, the research can be useful for higher education institutions, schools and training centers. With the help of the proposed model, it provides insight into the possibilities of predicting the score that applicants can score in entrance exams to higher education institutions.

MAE (Mean Absolute Error) is used as a measure to evaluate how close the model data is to the experimental data. It is a simple and understandable indicator that is widely used in various fields, including predictive modeling. A lower MAE value indicates a better prediction.

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i - \hat{x}_i| \quad (8)$$

MSE (Mean Squared Error) is a measure of the accuracy of the predictive model by calculating the average value of the square of the differences between the predicted values and the actual values.

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \hat{x}_i)^2 \quad (9)$$

RMSE (Root Mean Square Error) is a popular metric used to evaluate the accuracy of predictive models. This is useful when the errors have a non-linear relationship with the dependent

variable. RMSE is a more reliable measure of model performance compared to other metrics such as MAE and MSE.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \hat{x}_i)^2} \quad (10)$$

Here, x_i is the actual value, and \hat{x}_i is the model result, that is, the predicted value.

The results of the above formulas used in the evaluation of the model are presented in Table 2.

Table 2.

	MAE	MSE	RMSE
Teaching data	0,12	0,11	0,12
Test data	0,21	0,20	0,38
Control data	0,24	0,22	0,34
Total	0,23	0,21	0,36

The scores that the applicants can get in the double exams were determined by the prediction model, and the mean absolute error between the determined value and the actual value was MAE 0,23. Similarly, the MSE value is 0,21. MSE assigns a larger value to larger variances, which can be useful in detecting larger errors in the model. The RMSE value is 0,36, and it is an effective tool in detecting model errors, as is the MSE value. The conclusion from the data

presented in Table 2 is that the developed ANFIS model was an effective forecasting model. In addition, the dataset was compared with other prediction models such as LinearRegression, Random Forest, XGBoost, DecisionTreeRegressor, and K-nearest Neighbors. In the table below, you can see a table comparing the result with other prediction models.

Table 3.

	MAE	MSE	RMSE
ANFIS model	0,23	0,21	0,36
LinearRegression	0,31	0,35	0,38
Random Forest	0,29	0,24	0,37
XGBoost	0,26	0,22	0,37
DecisionTreeRegressor	0,28	0,26	0,39
K-nearest Neighbors	0,30	0,35	0,40

Based on the comparison of ANFIS model with other prediction models, it is seen that ANFIS model outperforms Linear Regression, Decision Tree Regressor and K-nearest Neighbors models in all three metrics: MAE, MSE and RMSE. The ANFIS model also performs better than Random Forest in terms of MAE and RMSE, but the MSE is slightly higher. However, the ANFIS model can be obtained.

The model was presented to users in the form of a website on the Internet. Since the input parameters are not focused on one discipline, the scope of application of the model has become much larger. That is the model, which uses the demographic and behavioral data of the applicants in the admission parameters, can be applied to all

applicants, not to those who are preparing in the field of mathematics or history.

Conclusion. In this study, we created a model and a website for predicting the success of applicants applying to higher education institutions in Uzbekistan based on neuro-fuzzy systems. The developed ANFIS model is considered the most effective method for predicting the success of applicants. Due to the fact that the variables of this model are not adapted to exactly one direction, it is suitable for applicants who are preparing for all directions. It was verified that the developed model works more accurately than other forecasting models. After that, a website was developed based on this model in order to create convenience for users. Through the website, it is possible to predict the score of the applicants

based on their demographic and behavioral data. This provides a convenient platform for applicants to enter their demographic and behavioral information and predict exam results. In addition, the model and website may be adapted for use in other countries or regions.

In addition, based on the estimated result, it is possible to develop a recommendation system

designed to direct applicants to a higher education institution that matches their capabilities. Overall, this study highlights the potential of using demographic and behavioral data-driven approaches to improve higher education admissions and demonstrates the effectiveness of the ANFIS model in predicting applicant success.

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